

TECHNOLOGIES OF APPLICATION OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION

Yodgorova Hilola Isroilovna

Jizzax Polytechnic Institute Senior teacher;

Shumkarova Shamsiya Po`latovna

Jizzax Polytechnic Institute Senior teacher;

Norboyeva Gulasal

Jizzax Polytechnic Institute assistant;

Tel.:99890-310-34-35

e-mail:hilolayodgorova@gmail.com

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Annotation. This article discusses aspects of reforming the education system in higher education institutions, in particular, the organization of effective lessons using digital technologies. Based on these studies, technologies have been developed and implemented to increase the interest and activity of students in the learning process.

Keywords: digital technologies, education, knowledge, integration, problem education, modern education, interactive, innovation.

In his next address to the Oliy Majlis, President Mirziyoyev called for the development of a national concept of digital economy, which envisages the modernization of all sectors of the economy on the basis of digital technologies, and on this basis to implement the Digital Uzbekistan - 2030 program. As we listen to the appeal, it is clear that the program is in the field of economics at first glance, but we, the teachers working in the field of education, feel that we have a great responsibility. Because the economic life of the country, reforms and the introduction of digital technologies in all areas, of course, can not bypass the field of education. On the contrary, the digital economy is based on human resources and education. Therefore, the future of digital Uzbekistan is in the hands of our students and young people sitting at school desks. Of course, if they have high-quality and modern knowledge that can manage and develop the digital economy,

our future will be great, and the security of digital Uzbekistan will be ensured. In my opinion, this requires focusing not only on the exact and natural sciences, but also on all subjects and their mother tongue education, which is a "threshold" for them. However, in addition to the language of computer science, the issue of training programmers who are literate in both foreign and native languages remains relevant. It is no secret that the important task of training competent and competent personnel for public administration, all spheres of state and society is not fully fulfilled.

The national concept of digital economy put forward by our President is for the Uzbek people, for a multinational Uzbekistan. This means that everyone, as well as everyone, should be involved in its construction and implementation.

The emphasis on digital education in the development of the digital economy program is reflected in the experience of many developed countries where the program is implemented. In particular, the Russian Federation pays special attention to this aspect. It is important to keep in mind that the integration of digital technology in education, especially in secondary schools, will be effective in the future. Experts say that accelerating the implementation of digital technologies in the teaching of all subjects in the curriculum of not only computer science, but also secondary schools will accelerate the implementation of long-term plans. However, there are exceptions in the introduction of digital technologies in education, such as the opposition to enlightenment, development, resistance to the introduction of any innovation, and the contradictions encountered. In particular, this is evident in the introduction of digital education.

In the age of globalization, teachers have a key role to play in shaping the country's innovative capabilities. Such an important task can be solved only by a teacher who is well versed in modern pedagogical and information technologies, constantly working on himself, improving his knowledge, skills and abilities, taking a creative approach to his work. "It is necessary to further improve the educational process, curricula and programs of higher education through the widespread introduction of new pedagogical technologies and teaching methods, qualitative updating of the scientific and educational process of master's degree and the introduction of modern organizational forms."

At a time when education is booming, education is not going to stay the same. Nowadays, the traditional forms of education: dialogue, memorization, non-traditional forms of education have been replaced by various forms of education: integrated lessons, observation lessons, problem-solving. Students like the lessons organized through these forms of education, they are interested in them, they are given a lot of news.

Modern education aims at the student: to acquire knowledge freely, to know how to interact with different people in different situations, and at the same time to feel free and confident. Therefore, the communicative technology of education is innovative in the process.

The process of education and upbringing can develop in an active form, without developing a person on its own. For the development of knowledge, skills and abilities of the student, it is necessary to organize his activities properly. There is no development in the process of poor comprehension of the learning material. For example, no matter how many pages a student reads, if he does not remember the numbers, he will not be able to learn to make examples from them, and he will not develop any problem-solving skills. The student's own actions will be the basis for the development of his / her abilities in the future. Therefore, the task of education is to create situations that motivate students to action. In short, teachers need to create a special learning environment that helps each student develop individual tools and methods to solve tasks correctly in different situations. This, in turn, is one of the most important issues in the technology of achieving results in the education system.

Higher education students are so distracted that it is often difficult for them to shift their focus from one state to another. However, the student's attention is enhanced when he or she is given the opportunity to change any object, electronic form, note, color, size, or shape on the board. For example, the use of computers, projectors, electronic whiteboards in teaching lectures and practical subjects increases the interest of students in the lessons and increases the activity of the educational process. The amount of information does not weigh on students. After all, the process, if used in new pedagogical technologies, allows for active learning. The electronic board is an effective tool for making the educational process in higher education institutions visual,

colorful and interesting. Digital technologies are very important in the development of the educational process.

In a classroom equipped with information and communication devices, it will be interesting and effective for students to organize and carry out the educational process.

Digital technology is a set of methods, production processes, and software that integrates the collection, editing, storage, distribution, and use of information for the benefit of the user.

Scientists say that the use of digital technologies in education should aim to address the following issues:

- Ensuring and developing the structure of students' thinking;
- support all types of student cognitive activities in the acquisition, development and strengthening of knowledge, skills and abilities;
- Implement the principle of individualization of the educational process while maintaining the integrity of the educational process.

Digital technologies can be categorized according to a number of indicators of educational tools:

1. On pedagogical issues:

a) basic training tools: textbooks, education systems, knowledge control systems;

b) practical training tools: problem sets, digital technologies, virtual constructors;

d) aids: literature, developmental computer games, multimedia video lessons;

2. On the organization of the educational process:

a) information and educational resources;

b) interactive;

Suggestions and recommendations. The use of digital technologies helps to increase students' interest and positive motivation, as it takes into account the individual educational opportunities and needs of students, a wide range of content and forms of education, reveals students' creative potential, helps students to master modern information technology. The possibilities of digital technology can be used to organize digital learning resources, individual tests and distance

learning. The widespread use of digital technologies and the provision of modern knowledge and skills in the field of education has become an urgent task.

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